

The CARE Principles

What are the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance?

Open data initiatives have neglected the complexities of Indigenous data governance and sovereignty, including tensions between, for example, protecting Indigenous rights to and interests in data by and about Indigenous communities and supporting open data, machine learning, data sharing, and big data initiatives.

The CARE Principles (as set out by the Global Indigenous Data Alliance) promote equitable participation in processes of data re-use processes “by shifting the focus from regulated consultation to value-based relationships that position data approaches within Indigenous cultures and knowledge systems for the benefit of Indigenous Peoples” (Castellano 2004; Anderson et al. 2003).

- ❖ Indigenous communities, peoples, and nations identify themselves as having a historical continuity with the pre-invasion and pre-colonial societies that developed on their territories and see themselves as distinct from other sectors of the societies that now dominate on those territories, or parts of them.
- ❖ The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance build on, integrate, and complement mainstream work on data re-use, but extend it to include actions and ethics that are aligned with the people and the purposes for which the data exist. CARE also addresses historical injustices by creating value from Indigenous data in ways that are grounded in Indigenous worldviews, and by creating opportunities for Indigenous peoples in the knowledge economy (cf. Carroll et al. 2019).

Tenets of the CARE Principles

- **Collective Benefit:** Support Indigenous (re-) use of data for policy making and service evaluation; creating data that reflects community values.
- **Authority to Control:** Control over data that support Indigenous governance, sovereignty and self-determination.
- **Responsibility:** Maintaining respectful relationships with Indigenous peoples from whom data originate or about whom data are collected.
- **Ethics:** Ensure the representation and participation of Indigenous peoples in assessing the benefits and harms associated with potential future (re-) use.

Aims of the CARE Principles

Designed to align data practices with **Indigenous knowledge and rights**, the CARE Principles are “people- and purpose-oriented, reflecting the crucial role of data in advancing innovation, governance, and self-determination among Indigenous Peoples” (Carroll et al. 2020). They **emphasize collective data ownership** and control to promote indigenous self-determination. These principles “address important considerations for modern data ecosystems and across data lifecycles” (ibid) and “describe high-level actions applicable within research, government, and institutional data settings” (ibid).

The ultimate goal is for data stewards and users of Indigenous data to implement the CARE and FAIR principles together (cf. Carroll et al. 2020).

What institutions have adopted the CARE principles?

Several institutions (see Carroll et al. 2019), including the Research Data Alliance (see Wyborn 2024), the Smithsonian Institution, and the Open Data Charter have adopted the CARE Principles.

Find citations and scholarly resources on CARE Principles and other topics in the EOSC SOA Group Library on Zotero.

